

Fig. D1. Morphometric PCA plot of seven informative fruiting traits (PC1-2 = 31.9, 18.8 %), based on analysis of 118 plants from all five Oregon *C. howellii* (CAHO) sites, including 3-yr populations HRA-HRA2, Hugo Rest Area. See also Fig. 3A. Sites in Table 1, Fig. 2 map.